

Articulations of the institutional and the popular in the construction of Europe: A discourse-theoretical analysis of Czech social media content

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Abstract

This article focuses on how Europe is discursively constructed across its institutional and popular dimensions, in content published on social media, in the Czech Republic. The research combines quantitative content analysis and discourse-theoretical analysis to explore both broader patterns and varied nuances of the institutional and the popular in the discursive construction of Europe. The analysis shows the hegemonic presence of institutional aspects and dimensions in articulating Europe, while the Europe of the people, of values and ideas, is not conspicuous. The discursive mechanisms of reduction and contestation activate specific articulations of the institutional and the popular, weakening the signifier Europe as a potential identity marker for Czech citizens. These mechanisms are activated by Eurosceptic populism, exacerbated during the research period of elections, in the Czech context that bears a post-socialist load in articulating national and European identities.

Keywords

Europe, European identity, social media, Czech Republic, discourse, institutions, people, popular

1 Introduction

The idea of Europe, and what it means to be European, does not have a single fixed meaning (Delanty & Rumford, 2005), but can take on different meanings which are subject to change and contestation, being the product of struggles around the preferred significations of what constructs Europe. The different approaches as to what Europe is and what informs people's sense of Europeanness, include both institutional and popular dimensions, in diverse combinations and intensities. What further complicates these constructions of Europeanness is that both the institutional (concerning institutions and formal struc-

tures) and the popular (concerning people or popular practices) may be perceived differently, taking on different formations and interpretations. These articulations intersect with diverse and competing ideas of regional, national, and supranational identities and identifications (Carpentier et al., 2023), being the product of political struggle themselves, and being embedded in hegemonic and counterhegemonic ideologies about identity and social organization.

To address these issues, this article studies how Europe is discursively constructed across its institutional and popular dimensions, in content published on social media, in the Czech Republic. The combined explo-

ration of these two key dimensions that inform the construction of Europe has so far attracted limited scholarly attention, which attests, we believe, to the relevance of this study. Social media are selected for this study as they are used as a space by institutional and non-institutional actors, news media, organizations, and individuals to share news, information, and opinions about issues of public concern, in our case about Europe. For the purposes of the study, Facebook and Twitter¹ posts related to European issues, published by professional news producers, institutional actors, and citizens, are analyzed, over a three-month period (September–November 2021). The research combines quantitative content analysis and discourse-theoretical analysis, supported by Laclau and Mouffe's (1985) discourse theory. The research is also informed by the scholarly work on institutional and popular approaches to politics, culture and social organization (Berger & Luckmann, 1967; Laclau, 2005; Williams, 2015), pertaining also to Europe (Delanty & Rumford, 2005; della Porta, 2020; Wodak & Boukala, 2015).

As will be elaborated later on, the analysis points to the hegemony of the institutional, at the expense of the popular, in the constructions of Europe. This is activated through a series of reductions in addressing Europe, which then facilitate Europe's contestation by populist and Eurosceptic voices. The latter are particularly vocal during the period of study, which is dominated by the parliamentary elections in the country and the COVID-19 pandemic (adding to the specificity of the research period), articulating Europe as not relevant or harmful for the Czech Republic and its people. Moreover, the findings concerning how the (non)identification with Europe is used as a constitutive outside for the construction of the Czech national identity merit broader reflection as to how nations across Europe negotiate their multiple identities, and attempt to relate to Europe and construct for themselves a particular kind of European-ness.

2 Theoretical and contextual framework

2.1 Discursive constructions of Europe across the institutional and the popular

This study is grounded in a discourse-theoretical perspective, inspired by Laclau and Mouffe's (1985) discourse theory and its later extensions (Carpentier, 2017), which approaches discourses as frameworks of intelligibility, or as ways of knowing the world. Discourse theory allows us to study the struggles over the articulation of particular knowledges about social reality, or discourses, and the struggles between these discourses to attain hegemonic positions (Laclau, 1990).

A discourse-theoretical approach is highly suited for the study of national or European identities, as it aligns with non-essentialist approaches, seeing identities as constructed in relation, juxtaposition, or opposition to a multitude of Others or constitutive outsides. This pluralist approach allows us to show that these identities have no stable essences but are discursively constructed, and that their related signifiers are objects of political struggle (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985), being contingent and subject to change. Hence, as it is demonstrated through this approach, there is not a single meaning or 'correct' definition of what Europe is, or what it means to be European (or Czech); rather different clusters of meanings, or discourses, circulate in the social realm, with their own ideological load, and with varying degrees of societal acceptance, some of which manage under certain conditions to attain hegemonic positions while others stay counter-hegemonic.

In this broad field of discursivity, two key dimensions that inform the construction of identities (concerning the (nation-)state, Europe, etc.) are of particular importance for our study. These are the dimensions of the institutional and the popular, which are also discursively constructed through political struggle.

Firstly, institutions—or what we can call the realm of the institutional—can be seen as “multifaceted, durable social structures, made up of symbolic elements, social activities, and material resources” (Scott, 2014, p.57). As Scott's definition highlights, institutions are constituent and constitutive of social

1 We maintain the former name of the social media platform X, given that this was the platform's name at the time of research.

life in a dynamic process. On the one hand, these ‘durable social structures’ enjoy dominance through the hegemonization of their discourses, through processes and mechanisms of, for instance, objectivation and reification (see Berger & Luckmann, 1967), through which institutions become articulated as living creatures, disconnected from human activities, and allocated a ‘proper’ discursive identity (see also Doudaki & Boubouka, 2020). At the same time, institutions are subject to (often minor or unnoticeable) change through social interaction and political struggle.

Second, also the people—and the popular—are discursively constructed. The term ‘popular’ has been defined among others as “actually made by the people for themselves” (Williams, 2015, p. 180) or as “belonging to the people” (Bourdieu, 2016, p. 32). For Badiou, the term ‘people’ is a “political category” (2016, p. 31), being both a force of emancipation (by the people) against colonial, imperialist, or other brutal domination, and a tool of suppression and domination (by the state against the people). Zooming in on these political uses of ‘the people,’ two key areas that offer clear constructions of the people (and that will be of importance in this article) are those offered by populism and nationalism. Populism, from a discourse-theoretical perspective, is founded on the opposition of the signifier ‘the people’ against the constitutive outside of the elite (Laclau, 2005). Nationalism, as Billig (1995, p. 24) argues, is articulated through the conjunction of the nation-as-people and the nation-as-state. Reflecting on these usages, De Cleen and Carpentier (2010, pp. 180–181) argue that populism and nationalism create different antagonisms and exclusions of the people, which can still co-exist, reinforcing one another. While in populist discourses, what is crucial is the up/down antagonism between the people and the elite, nationalist discourses are based on an in/out distinction nations (and peoples).

The institutional and the popular intersect with the construction of Europe. As literature shows, the political-institutional components of European governance (Carpentier et al., 2023, p. 117; Olsen, 2002) enjoy higher visibility and prominence. These ar-

ticulations have a strong emphasis on “how (part of) Europe is governed, how authority and power are distributed, exercised and controlled, [and] how institutions are organized” (Carpentier et al., 2023, p. 117). This preoccupation with Europe’s governing and regulatory institutions has become stronger in the context of the European Union project, in a process that has been labelled EUisation (Flockhart, 2010). EUisation has a strong regulatory dimension, as EU’s operations are bolstered by a regulatory body of institutions that support political processes and governance through a “coherent body of rules (*iuris corpus*) of a supranational character that binds the Members States of the European Union” (Ferreira, 2009, p. 171). This strong emphasis on the EU and its institutions impacts on how Europe is constructed and on the sense of belonging in the European assemblage shared among the European countries and communities. Moreover, the emphasis “on how policies are created and then become (or not) part of the policy regime of the EU member states” (Carpentier et al., 2023, p. 117) appears to have normalizing and disciplining effects for the entire European assemblage.

Reactions against these homogenizing tendencies take diverse forms and are often grouped under the denominator of Euroscepticism. A Eurosceptic is described as “someone who is opposed to the powers of the European Union” (Brack & Startin, 2015, p. 239), which is more broadly related to a distrust in and dissatisfaction with EU policies and institutions (Bărgăoanu et al., 2015). Euroscepticism is also connected with ethnocentric or nationalist approaches that see the European and national identities as competing, incompatible or in a clear hierarchization, where the national identity is either the only authentic one or the strongest and most important one (see Wodak & Boukala, 2015; Wodak et al., 2009). In this vein, supranational governance and regulation at the EU level are seen as threatening the nation states’ independence, assaulting their national sovereignty (Wodak & Boukala, 2015). Also, as articulated in ethnopopulist discourses, the EU becomes the enemy of the ‘authentic’ Europe and its people (Hegedüs, 2019; Sata, 2023).

The popular—even though it might be less present in comparison to the institu-

tional dimension—brings in the European people. In this construction Europe is understood as “constituted by its people, materialized as bodies who share the same territory” (Carpentier et al., 2023, p. 112). Ostergren and Le Bossé (2011, p. 8) “prefer to define Europe ... as a uniform denoted region, a realm whose people share a cultural tradition that sets them apart from peoples elsewhere in the world”. In these representations of the European people, issues that are addressed concern aspects of European territory, culture, values, communication and interactions, citizenship, and civil society (expressed also through social movements) (see e.g., Bellamy et al., 2006; Delanty & Rumford, 2005; della Porta, 2020). The articulations of the people in these cases are founded on either essentialist or pluralist approaches to identity, often echoing either right-wing ethnocentric or nationalist approaches to the people as (pure) national/European subjects, or left-wing understandings emphasizing European people’s solidarity and common struggles. Obviously, both the left-wing and right-wing approaches to the people may be either populist or Eurosceptic.

2.2 Populism and Euroscepticism in the Czech Republic

These constructions of Europe become invoked in particular ways in the Czech context, where populism and Euroscepticism have an important presence. Going back to the post-communist era in the 1990s, the hegemonic discourse in the Czech Republic articulated the country’s membership to the EU as a return home to the ‘European family’ and to the West (see Havlík, 2011; Kim, 2020), distancing the country from its communist past. This discourse lost some of its power in the 2000s, as the challenges of the European integration became visible (Havlík, 2011, p. 130). During this period, a series of interlinked processes were observed in the country, which affected the sentiment towards Europe and the EU. These processes were related to the oligarchization of politics and media, the high concentration of power among such oligarchs, and the rise of extreme populist rhetorics and anti-EU attitudes (Hanley & Vachudova, 2018). Recent key figures in these trends have been the Czech former prime minister, leader of ANO (Action

of Dissatisfied Citizens) and businessman, Andrej Babiš, and the leader of far-right SPD (Freedom and Direct Democracy), Tomio Okamura. While the former is characterized by ‘soft’ Euroscepticism (Havlík & Holoušek, 2021), the latter is a radical opponent of the European Union and calls for the Czech state to leave the EU, in a so-called ‘Czechxit’.

The rise of populism in the Czech political scene which can be traced in the mid-2010s, is seen as connected with the growing dissatisfaction with the post-1989 party politics triggered by the corruption scandals of the traditional political parties (Císař & Štětka, 2017). During the same period, migration was extensively framed as a threat by populists (Wondreys, 2021) arguing, through securitization rhetorics, for the enhanced need to safeguard national autonomy. In these debates, Europe and the EU were presented as a menace, aligning with Eurosceptic sentiments among the Czech public and political parties. These voices have been largely echoing what is called Eurosceptic populism (Csehi & Zgut, 2020, p. 54), in which “critique against the EU is used to crystallize anti-elitism and people-centrism”. Eurosceptic populism has a specific undertone in Central Eastern Europe and in the Czech Republic more specifically, given the region’s history, formerly known as the Eastern Bloc, as it feeds from the collective trauma of the Soviet past (Hloušek & Kaniok, 2020), activating feelings of frustration against domination, subordination and humiliation.

Vochocová and Rosenfeldová (2022) ascribe a special role to the post-socialist resentment in constructing anti-European discourses and generally negative representations of the EU, in the Czech Republic. In their study of online discussions concerning migration, the authors found clear traces of the post-socialist heritage as expressed in the Czech users’ online comments critiquing the EU as “‘leftist’ (socialist or neo-Marxist), bureaucratic and inefficient”. For the authors, this “may stem from the historical trauma of a country controlled by a socialist administration, which resulted in not only political and cultural, but also economic isolation and marginalization of the CEE countries in the European context” (Vochocová & Rosenfeldová, 2022, p. 10).

3 Research design, methods and study period

This article studies how Europe is discursively constructed in content published on social media platforms, in the Czech Republic. Social media platforms are used broadly by institutional and non-institutional actors in the country, for the circulation of news and opinion about current affairs. At the time of research, YouTube, Facebook and Instagram were the most used social networks in the Czech Republic among the general population (AMI Digital, 2021), while Twitter was used more by media professionals and experts.

For the purposes of the study, Facebook (individual pages and public Facebook groups) and Twitter posts related to European issues were extracted and analyzed, covering a three-month period (September–November 2021). The research focused on posts published by professional, non-professional, institutional and non-institutional actors (i.e. news media, non-media organizations, political agents and citizens).²

The selection of the posts was driven by key themes and issues that (a) pertain to Europe, and (b) are of the highest concern for European citizens. According to the Eurobarometer of 2020 (European Commission, 2020), the issues of highest concern for the Europeans were health, economy and the environment. Sets of keywords (lexicons) were developed for each of the main research themes – Europe, health, economy and the environment (the last three always in relation to Europe). The lexicons that drove the post extraction were developed by first including five to ten keywords related to these main themes and then continuing with searches in Google, on Facebook and Twitter, to identify “words or concepts that were most frequently associated with” the main themes and the initially identified keywords (Cardoso et al., 2021, p. 14; see also Rogers, 2017). The final lexicons included approximately 50 main keywords per theme (Europe, health, economy, environment), with additional variations, synonyms and declinations of these main keywords. Such keywords were, for instance, health, COVID,

vaccine, disease, hospital, economy, salary, finance, tax, unemployment, inflation, business, energy, environment, climate, pollution, nature, global warming, Europe, EU, European Commission, regulation, Euro, member state, etc.

All relevant Facebook and Twitter posts (i.e. posts that included any of the defined keywords), published during September–November 2021 were extracted using Crowdtangle (for Facebook) and Brandwatch (for Twitter).³ These two tools for data extraction operated at the time of research within the framework of the authorized API (Application Programming Interface) for each of these social media platforms. Only publicly available posts and data were extracted, accessible through these APIs, and compliant with GDPR terms. The extracted posts were then ranked on the basis of overall highest interactions (for Facebook) and estimated reach (for Twitter), for each of the three months of the research period. Using the metrics that the social media platforms themselves provide to have a measurement of popularity has its limitations, the biggest of which is that these metrics are developed, owned and controlled by the platforms themselves (see Cardoso et al., 2021, p. 24). Notwithstanding the limitations, this method allowed to estimate popularity and gather evidence on the content and posts that were relevant and/or influential in the public debate on the issues of Europe, health, environment and economy, during the research period, in the specific platforms.

The ten most popular posts (on the basis of interactions or reach) were selected for the analysis, from each main theme, social media type, research month and whether they were published by news media or not. This selection method allowed for the analysis of adequate relevant content across all research aspects and dimensions. After filtering out non-relevant content (i.e., posts that did not have a clear European dimension or that did not explicitly address health, economy or the environment), the final dataset comprised 566 posts. Selecting and analyzing social media content on the basis of popularity, published by both

2 For the detailed criteria and methods of post extraction, see Cardoso et al. (2021).

3 Dates of post extraction: September 2021: 06/12/2021; October 2021: 12/05/2022; November 2021: 01/06/2022.

institutional and non-institutional actors is consistent with the aim of this research, to study dimensions of both the institutional and the popular, also in relation to the content's publishing agents. The publishing agents in our study consisted of four main categories: professional news media, political agents (political parties and individual politicians), organizations (other than media and political parties), and regular citizens (any individual not belonging to / representing / speaking as a member of an organization, political party, institution, media organization).

In order to have a broader overview of the constructions of Europe, but also to scrutinize (a selection of) the posts more in detail, the research combined the methods of quantitative content analysis (Krippendorff, 2004) and the tools of discourse-theoretical analysis (Carpentier & De Cleen, 2007). In particular, we first explored broader patterns in relation to the aspects and dimensions that construct Europe over the sample of 566 posts, and then analyzed in depth articulations of the institutional and the popular in the discursive construction of Europe in a more targeted sample.

Hence, 566 posts were first subjected to a quantitative content analysis, to identify which issues and aspects of European relevance these posts address. All techniques of anonymization and non-traceability of individual users' identities were applied in the analysis and reporting of the findings. Two researchers acted as main coders, following extensive training by a third researcher (all three are among the co-authors of the article). The two researchers coded independently 46% of the same sample of posts with the purpose of measuring the inter-coder agreement levels. Krippendorff's alpha range for the project's variables was 0.738–1.000⁴, which is considered of adequate reliability (Krippendorff, 2004). After reaching adequate inter-coder

agreement levels, the rest of the posts were shared among and coded by the two coders.

The aspects and dimensions that were coded for this research, transformed into variables (see Tables 1–2), were identified using the relevant literature as a guide, adjusted to serve the purposes of the study. Several aspects and dimensions could be identified in each analyzed post, which all needed to have a clear European relevance (minimally involving two or more European countries, or parts of Europe). Apart from aspects and dimensions of European relevance, the quantitative content analysis focused on the publishing agents of the posts (media, political actors, citizens and organizations) and the sentiment of the posts towards Europe (positive, negative or neutral).

A subset of 100 posts was then analyzed using qualitative coding techniques, common in textual analysis (Saldaña, 2013). The material was analyzed in its entirety by one of the article's authors, a second author coded approximately 20% of the posts, a third author acted as a main reviewer and validator of the main analytical categories, and the fourth and fifth authors acted as supportive reviewers-validators of the analytical model. The sensitizing concepts—to guide our analysis—were provided by the discourse-theoretical concepts together with the concepts from the theoretical framework that addressed the discursive constructions of Europe, and the institutional and popular aspects of the social. Starting from an open coding process, the analytical categories that structure our analysis were developed through several coding cycles, supported by our sensitizing concepts, in a retroductive process (see Glynos & Howarth, 2007).

The research period (September–November 2021) was dominated by the parliamentary elections held in the Czech Republic on 8–9 October 2021. Populist rhetoric and polarization, centered around the handling of the COVID-19 pandemic, migration, corruption, and the economy monopolized the public discourse, also on social media. Prime minister Andrej Babiš, leader of populist party ANO—who was then defeated at the election by the center-right SPOLU coalition—focused on the 'migration crisis' and used the opportunity of the COVID-19 pandemic to

4 The detailed results of Krippendorff's alpha coefficient were the following: Publishing agents: Media = 1.000; Political agent = 1.000; Citizen = 0.957; Organization = 1.000 // European dimension: Institutions = 0.963; Economies–Industries = 0.884–0.926; Law = 0.956; Politics = 0.922; Democracy = 0.738; Science = 0.821; Values = 0.904; Territory = 0.871; People–Interactions = 0.908; Public sphere = 1.000; Culture = 0.856 // Sentiment = 0.946.

showcase his connection with ordinary people (Císař & Kubát, 2021). Important in this context is that Babiš's government had been under investigation by the EU for conflict of interest and misuse of EU funds. As it was stated in the 2021 European Commission audit report, "prime minister, Mr Babiš exercised influence on the allocation of EU subsidies to Agrofert, an agro-chemical conglomerate that he founded himself", which had been, at the time of investigation, still receiving subsidies from EU funds (European Commission, 2021). The extreme right-wing populist party SPD, led by Tomio Okamura, accelerated its anti-EU rhetoric, raising 'Czechxit' as one of the main items of the political party's campaign. SPD was by far the most prominent publishing agent, in the social media posts analyzed, among the political actors, followed by Babiš's ANO. To be noted is that SPD did not see its position improved since the election of 2017, still receiving close to 10% of the votes (McEnchroe, 2021).

4 Research findings and analysis

In order to study broad patterns of how Europe is constructed in Czech social media content, a quantitative content analysis was first performed. The analysis provided important insights into how Europe is constructed (primarily) across its institutional and (less) across its popular dimensions by the different studied actors. Informed by these findings, the discourse-theoretical analysis zoomed in and explored in detail the mechanisms of reduction and contestation that activate these constructions of Europe.

4.1 Dimensions of Europe on Czech social media: An emphasis on the institutional and a disregard of the popular

One of the main variables used for this quantitative content analysis of Facebook posts ($n=344$, 61%) and Tweets ($n=222$, 39%) was the publishing agent, which had four categories. More than half of the posts were published by 'media agents' ($n=295$, 52%), while 'political agents' ($n=135$, 24%) and 'citizens' ($n=125$, 22%) published close to one-fourth and one-fifth of the posts respectively. The re-

maining posts were published by 'other organizations' ($n=12$, 2%). The sentiment analysis used three categories, with the first one, 'neutral / no sentiment', applying to almost three quarters of the posts ($n=417$, 74%). The remaining quarter was almost exclusively 'negative' ($n=142$, 25%), with only 7 posts (1%) coded as 'positive'.

A more detailed bivariate analysis shows a strong focus on institutional aspects of Europe, combined with a focus on economic, legal, regulatory and political dimensions of Europe, again mainly through an institutional prism (see Table 1). The Europe of the people, of values, culture and democracy is much less visible in the analyzed posts, and is regularly related to a negative sentiment towards Europe (see Table 2). These patterns are consistent, with some variations, regardless of whether the posts are published by institutional agents or citizens.

As Table 1 shows, the great majority of the posts (75%) have a reference to the European institutions such as the European Commission, the European Parliament and the European Council. These posts are published by all types of publishing agents (69% of the media posts, 84% of the political agent posts, 78% of the citizen posts and 75% of the organization posts, concern European institutions). As Table 2 shows, the majority of these posts are neutral; still, close to one-third of them (31%) bear an explicitly negative tone as it concerns Europe and its institutions. This negativity is frequently connected to a populist or Euro-sceptic discourse, which focuses on how the EU and its institutions do not promote but rather harm the interests of the Czech state.

European economies and industries appear in more than half of the posts (57%), again, published by all types of publishing agents (see Table 1). These posts bear an economic dimension of European relevance, concerning the state of the economy or the economic policies in (parts of) Europe. They bear also references to diverse kinds of financial, business or industrial activity, in different sectors, in Europe. Occasionally they involve unemployment, poverty, economic fraud and corruption. Close to one-third of these posts (30%) communicate a negative sentiment as it concerns Europe (see Table 2). Negative-sentiment posts, often published by Eu-

Table 1: Overview of European dimensions and publishing agents

European dimension (Eu. di)	Posts		Media		Political agent		Citizen		Organization	
	<i>n</i>	% <i>N</i> (=566)	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di
Institutions	422	74.6	198	46.9	117	27.7	99	23.5	8	1.9
Economies – Industries	320	56.5	164	51.3	86	26.9	65	20.3	5	1.6
Law	301	53.2	150	49.8	80	26.6	68	22.6	3	1.0
Politics	177	31.3	62	35.0	75	42.4	35	19.8	5	2.8
Democracy	70	12.4	19	27.1	40	57.1	11	15.7	0	0.0
Science	68	12.0	41	60.3	15	22.1	11	16.2	1	1.5
Values	62	11.0	13	21.0	35	56.5	14	22.6	0	0.0
Territory	59	10.4	26	44.1	26	44.1	6	10.2	1	1.7
People – Interactions	40	7.0	24	60.0	6	15.0	9	22.5	1	2.5
Public sphere	10	1.8	7	70.0	1	10.0	0	0.0	2	20.0
Culture	8	1.4	2	25.0	0	0.0	6	75.0	0	0.0

Table 2: Overview of European dimensions and sentiment towards Europe

European dimension (Eu. di)	Posts		Sentiment					
	<i>n</i>	% <i>N</i> (=566)	Neutral		Negative		Positive	
	<i>n</i>	% <i>N</i> (=566)	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di	<i>n</i>	% Eu. di
Institutions	422	74.6	285	67.5	131	31.0	6	0.2
Economies – Industries	320	56.5	222	69.4	95	29.7	3	0.1
Law	301	53.2	190	63.1	108	35.9	3	0.1
Politics	177	31.3	106	59.9	66	37.3	5	0.4
Democracy	70	12.4	31	44.3	37	52.9	2	0.4
Science	68	12.0	57	83.8	11	16.2	0	0.0
Values	62	11.0	24	38.7	36	58.1	2	0.5
Territory	59	10.4	34	57.6	25	42.4	0	0.0
People – Interactions	40	6.0	33	82.5	7	17.5	0	0.0
Public sphere	10	1.8	9	90.0	1	10.0	0	0.0
Culture	8	1.4	8	100	0	0.0	0	0.0

rosceptics and the far-right, attack the EU economic policies as destructive, and stress how much the independence of the national industries is limited or harmed by the European directives and their related legislation. Also, at times, the right-wing populist ANO critiques the EU policies for not supporting the Czech industries, and connects the country's economic and national independence with the choice to maintain the Czech crown as the national currency, not joining the Eurozone.

More than half of the posts (53%, see Table 1) include references to Europe's or EU's regulatory framework, directives, legislation, or legal decisions, again published by all agent types and often critiqued by the far-right as restricting the country's freedom and sovereignty, through negative-sentiment posts (36%, see Table 2). This thematic category also involves references to the Czech Republic and prime minister Babiš being under investigation by the European Commission for conflict of interest and misuse of EU subsidies allocated to Agrofert, the conglomerate founded by Babiš.

The examination of whether the published content has a clear political dimension showed that close to one-third of the posts (31%) address a political aspect at the European level (Table 1), involving political agreements or negotiations between political entities from different European countries, regarding political, economic or other issues. 37% of these posts have a negative tone (Table 2), often published by (far-right) voices who argue that this political activity is damaging the interests and wellbeing of the Czech people. An issue that attracted high interest and polarization during the research period was the EU's Green Deal policy, which was attacked by the (far-)right, as it was considered to be destructive for the Czech economy.

Posts referring to (European) democracy (12%), science (12%), European values (11%), and the European territory (10%) feature with a mild frequency (Table 1). Interestingly, the posts regarding the state of European democracy, or democracies within Europe, are mostly negative (53%) (Table 2). Such posts echo sometimes Eurosceptic voices that see the democratic freedoms of the Czech state being restrained by the EU structures. The posts that refer to a scientific aspect of European rele-

vance (12%) relate mostly to the COVID-19 pandemic, and concern issues and topics such as the efficiency and sufficiency of vaccines and other medication for the protection against COVID-19, and the EU vaccination policy. Such posts echo sometimes anti-vaccination views.

References to European values relate to the ideals and ideas of freedom, tolerance, solidarity, equality and non-discrimination, in Europe or as part of the European civilization. These references are more frequently negative (58%) than neutral or positive (Table 2), as they echo concerns that these European values are being threatened or not adhered to by the European countries. Also, the appeal to these values is sometimes made by far-right voices, to accuse Europe of being hypocritical. The posts that address issues pertaining to the European territory have a clear focus on Europe as a geographical space, with frequent references to its material borders, and the right or the need to protect them, addressed usually by right-wing, nationalist and Eurosceptic voices (negative references 42%). References to the European people, or interactions and dialogues of people in Europe, appear infrequently (Table 1). Other aspects, such as the European public sphere, or the European cultures, feature only rarely.

4.2 The mechanisms of reduction and contestation in articulating Europe: A discourse-theoretical analysis

Our discourse-theoretical analysis showed that two main discursive mechanisms activate the institutional and popular constructions of Europe, in the analyzed material. The first is the mechanism of reduction and the second is the mechanism of contestation. These mechanisms do not work in isolation but rather together, reinforcing the particular constructions of (the institutional and the popular in/of) Europe.

4.2.1 Reduction

The discourse-theoretical analysis showed that the constructions of Europe were limited in scope, and that this limited span—which we call a reductionist articulation of Europe, as it does not do justice to Europe's diversity of articulatory options—has a clear political nature. One main reduction is Europe's contrac-

tion to a particular territory, through the equation of Europe with the European Union. While Europe is reduced to the EU, the EU is expanded to represent the entire of Europe, politically, institutionally, culturally and geographically. Directives, decisions and policies at the EU level are often labelled as European, while the terms Europe and EU are used interchangeably in the posts, whether they are published by media, political actors or citizens. EUisation, which is becoming a hegemonic process in the construction of Europe, does not concern only the geographical-material shrinkage of Europe to the EU territory, but involves also Europe's identification with an institutionalized, technocratic assemblage which is imposing its political culture, becoming the canon of governance, and of social and economic organization, for the entire Europe.

This signification reflects also established ideas of institutionalized power leading to further reductions. Formulations in the posts about Europe or the EU being equated with "Brussels", with "Germany" or "Berlin", are frequent, indicating which actors are considered the centers of power in Europe. For example, the EU is framed as a "superstate under the hegemony of Germany and France"⁵ (Facebook, political agent, September 2021). Similarly, another post explains

how Germany (Merkel) simply and subtly controlled the whole of Europe with its new ideology (climate) and turned it into a puppet. Step by step, Europe is pandering only to German national interests, including the necessary and controllable economic dominance. The EU is just a cover here. (Twitter, citizen, September 2021)

Furthermore, these equations are built on, and strengthen, a number of exclusions, as to who is or shall be considered European. Two main reductions that activate exclusion were identified in the analysis. One relates to the EU members articulated as worthy members of the European family. Hence, non-EU Balkan countries and certain Central Eastern European countries are not articulated as members of the 'European family', or are being signified as not European enough. Especially

Russia and Belarus appear as Europe's major constitutive outsides, in articulations that invoke the Czech Republic's traumatic communist past, as becomes visible in this post: "Warsaw has a choice. Either it will mentally join Europe and accept migrants, or it will side with the Russian and Belarusian rulers, for whom human life has no greater value than a well-oiled Kalashnikov" (Twitter, media, November 2021). The second reduction is constructed through a series of rankings within the EU of more and less worthy member states, as the previous reference to Warsaw already showed. This second reduction is also visible in the following example: "Romania and Bulgaria have become the black sheep of the European Union. They have the lowest numbers of vaccinated population [against COVID-19] and at the same time the highest numbers of infected and hospitalized" (Facebook, media, October 2021).

Other reductions can be mapped out on the institutional and popular dimensions. First, Europe is constructed through the EU institutions. This type of reduction, activated also through the equation of Europe with the EU, in a process where one reduction is strengthening the other, heavily supports a construction of Europe as existing primarily through its institutions, promoting an institutionalized top-down culture of governance, in a model of powerful institutions and weak citizens. There is a strong focus in the analyzed posts, on how Europe or the EU is or shall be governed and how its institutions shall be organized, while there is no equal attention to its people. In this reduction, while institutions are highly visible and prominent, people are withdrawn in the background. This is activated through the construction of Europe's institutions, their operations and structures, as too complicated and blackboxed, reserved for the elite of experts and dissociated from the people, who do not possess the knowledge to comprehend their operations. In such a signification activated through reification, European institutions become more relevant than European people, in a process where institutions are attributed agency and people are deprived of it.

The invocation of the institutional is regularly present through datafication, a mechanism in which EU data and statistics pro-

5 All excerpts have been translated from Czech into English by the authors.

duced by expert bureaucracies, are used as the benchmark of the Czech Republic's and other countries' performance (echoing success, wellbeing, prosperity, failure), and as the measurement of their Europeanness. We read the following in a post referring to recently released EU statistics:

Babiš's government has successfully managed the Czech economy, in the last eight years. [...] The Czech Republic is richer than Italy, Greece or Spain, the Czechs are more satisfied than the French, Belgians or the British. [...] We did not catch up with the Germans in wages, but we overtook the French in overall satisfaction. [...] Czechs remain the richest of the countries of the former Eastern Bloc, they are on average two and a half times richer than neighboring Slovaks. (Facebook, citizen, September 2021)

In some occasions, normative appeals to Europe or the EU are made, addressing it as an institution that is governed, or that it shall be governed, by the rule of law, contributing to elevating the states' quality of justice and democratic governance. Through these representations the EU is articulated as supporting or pushing states to fight corruption, to improve their legislation in protecting human rights, gender rights, equality and non-discrimination, or in protecting the environment. In these claims, the emphasis is again on the institutional power of the EU to implement the rule of law and less on the people, in the name of whom these claims are usually made.

Also, the popular dimension of Europe becomes reduced, as Europe's citizens are articulated as an aggregation of national subjects. This institutionalized discourse about Europe does not give visibility to its citizens as European subjects. They rather appear as exclusively or primarily national subjects, in our case as Czech citizens. When they are addressed as both Czech and European, there is always a hierarchization prioritizing the national subject; thus the European subject does not exist unless subdued under the identity of the Czech-national subject. This reduction echoes essentialist approaches to identity, that are at odds with the acceptance of coexisting multiple identities. Such essentialist approaches consider the national iden-

tity as the most important or as the only 'real' one, whereas attributes such as 'European' are at best qualifiers of the national identity. This becomes stronger in the right-wing nationalist-populist discourse, where people are equated with the nation. From this perspective, claims made in the posts that people are not represented in Europe or the EU, mean that the Czech nation is not represented in Europe or the EU. In the following example, in which the EU is seen as the enemy of the European states, activated through the mechanism of contestation which will be elaborated further on, the reduction concerns the hierarchization or incompatibility of national and European or EU legal systems, when it comes to state sovereignty:

Poland is currently fighting not only for itself, but also sets the mirror of the whole European Union. The Visegrad Four has support only with Hungary, which is primarily our shame, but it is so large and populous that it can afford a proud resistance. It is an independent and sovereign state whose laws are above those created by the lunatics in Brussels. It should be so here too. (Facebook, citizen, October 2021)

In such cases, (European) people tend to appear as powerless, passive recipients of benefits or harm by Europe or the EU. They are at best the beneficiaries of this institutionalized Europeanness, without exercising agency in constructing some kind of Europeanness and some kind of identity for them, as European people. This articulation is not only manifest in the posts published by political actors or the media, but also in those by citizens. Citizens hardly use a popular ('of the people'), grassroots discourse about Europe, in the posts they publish, but tend to replicate the arguments, positions and vocabulary of institutional actors, who are treated as experts in their articulations of Europe. Hence, the dichotomy of powerful structures and institutions vis-a-vis weak and passive citizens in Europe, is maintained and replicated in public debate, significantly limiting the articulatory options of the European people. For instance, posts by citizens concerning the EU environmental policy under the Green Deal focus on the economic harm inflicted upon citizens. The Green Deal is presented as prof-

iting only the industry and specific economic interests, while the people are reduced to being the victims of the EU policies through an economic framing:

Expenses on [the Green Deal] will reach a trillion euros. And what does this mean to you? Prohibition of internal combustion engines for 13 years. Ecological taxes for most citizens.... layoffs of employees. Significant increase in energy prices. Czech debt for decades ahead. (Facebook, citizen, September 2021)

4.2.2 *Contestation*

The second main mechanism is that of contestation, through which the construction of Europe as valuable or relevant, is being challenged or attacked via its reductions. By reducing Europe to the EU and presenting it as an institutional apparatus, and by removing agency from the (European) people and presenting them as national subjects, the European assemblage can easily be contested as not relevant or harmful for the people and the nations in Europe. Our analysis shows that in particular Czech populist and nationalist voices are strong (and even viral) in the period examined (which, to be reminded, is an election period), in contesting Europe. These voices, being to a large extent part of the political elite themselves, attempt to align with ‘the people’ by artificially distancing themselves from the EU. This populist Euroscepticism is still addressed with regard to EU’s institutions, not offering alternatives for a more participatory, democratic Europe for all, but serving an ethnocentric sentiment by replacing one antagonism (the elite vs. the people) with another (the EU vs. the Czech people).

As previously mentioned, at the level of politics and governance, the EU features as an entity with very powerful institutions, or as a supra-institution itself, whose complex structure and operations are labyrinthine, opaque and blackboxed. Frequently, the EU is labelled in the posts as a “Berlin” or “Brussels empire” (Facebook, citizen, September 2021), or as a “superstate” led by Germany and France (Facebook, political agent, September 2021). This contestation centers around the idea that the EU is an apparatus that exercises excessive control over the Czech state, by forcing the latter to political

dependency on the EU. Thus, the Czech Republic loses sovereignty, being transformed to a “Brussels/Berlin protectorate” (Facebook, citizen, September 2021). In some posts, “Brussels” is being condemned for interfering with Czech national politics or for attacking the Czech government. The EU is portrayed also as a non-democratic institution, described as a “dictatorship” (Facebook, citizen, September 2021), or, again invoking the Czech history, as an institution promoting “the construction of red-green European communism, where they are equal and some are more equal” (Twitter, citizen, October 2021).

Furthermore, when an economic dimension is invoked, the EU features as a bureaucratic structure where business and the economy are prioritized over politics and over the European people. Within this framework, Europe or the EU appear as an apparatus of economic dominance (of Germany), promoting global capitalism, killing state self-sufficiency and creating economic dependency for the Czech Republic. The harmonized EU economic policies appear as damaging the Czech national economy (e.g., as it concerns energy) and leaving the domestic business activity unprotected (e.g., as it concerns the car industry). Two main populist antagonisms are articulated in relation to the economy. The first takes the form of an EU vs. the nation state / Czech Republic antagonism, as becomes visible in this post:

The European Union is not only not helping us, but harming us, and globalism is destroying nation states and their ability to fulfil basic functions for their citizens. Therefore, it is necessary to withdraw from the European Union and restore the self-sufficiency of our state. (Facebook, political agent, September 2021)

The second populist antagonism is structured as an EU vs. the (Czech) people opposition, in which the EU is an institution that supports the interests of the wealthy at the expense of the non-wealthy, as this post indicates: “but thanks to his [Babiš’s] work in politics, Agrofert receives billions of subsidies from the EU and now from our state treasury, which are intended for small and medium-sized enterprises” (Facebook, citizen, September 2021).

Europe's contestation touches upon the field of law and regulation as well. In this case, Europe and the EU are constructed as having been transformed into a regulative, disciplinary, normalizing bureaucratic system of surveillance and control. This is highlighted in the following example, which concerns the Czech Republic's obligation to digitize its public administration, something that is described in the post as surveillance, while the authority of the EU to impose such a regulation on the Czech state is contested: "So, instead of helping the government, the republic, they were only harming, they were pulling here [...] some crazy 'inspectors' from the EU, to properly 'cure' us, the state, the citizens" (Facebook, citizen, September 2021). The EU institutions and legislation thus become articulated as damaging the national interests through the pressure to homogenize all main sectors of social life (economy, health, environment, ...), for the member states. This is seen as assaulting 'Czechness', as what is considered the Czech unique identity, culture and values are being forced to change.

Finally, there is an underlying contestation in some of the posts, articulated through Euroscepticism, that the EU harms the 'real' Europe. For example, one of the extreme-right posts, which is asking for "Czechxit", warns for the need of "preserving the European character of our countries against multiculturalism" (Facebook, political agent, September 2021). However, this claim is based on an essentialist approach to Europe's identity, and is used as a pretext to hide the main argument that the primary or the only 'real' identity is the national-Czech identity. Also, in another post referring to the EU vaccination policy against COVID-19 and to the vaccination rates in non-European countries, it is emphasized that "Europe is falling apart and ethnic Europeans are committing mass suicide. What is the rate of 'vaccination' in NO GO zones [areas not allowed to travel due to pandemic restrictions]? I think 0.000. It is in them that the future owners of Europe live" (Twitter, political agent, October 2021). According to the author, the 'real' Europe and its people are threatened by non-Europeans who will own Europe in the future, due to the EU migration policies.

5 Discussion and conclusion

This study focused on how Europe is discursively constructed on Czech social media (Facebook and Twitter) through its institutional and popular articulations, combining quantitative content analysis and discourse-theoretical analysis. Analyzing social media selected on the basis of popularity, published by institutional and non-institutional actors, news media, organizations and individuals, supports the research aims to study dimensions of both the institutional and the popular, as it concerns both content and the content's publishing agents. The combined analysis first explored broader patterns in relation to the elements that construct Europe and then delved into the particularity of the articulations of the institutional and the popular in the discursive construction of Europe, in Czech social media content. Examining the core dimensions of the institutional and popular together allowed to bring to light how they inform one another in the construction of identities, and to consider ways to move beyond the sometimes restrictive elite/people antagonism of populist considerations (i. e., not automatically equating the institutional with the elite and the popular with populist apprehensions).

The analysis showed the dominance of institutional aspects and dimensions in addressing Europe, while the Europe of the people, ideas and values is hardly present in the analyzed posts, regardless of whether the posts are published by institutional agents or citizens. The discourse-theoretical analysis then identified reduction and contestation as the two discursive mechanisms that activate specific articulations of the institutional and the popular in the construction of Europe, enabling the hegemonization of the institutional, and discursively narrowing the signifier Europe, as a potential identity marker for Czech citizens. These mechanisms are activated by a Eurosceptic populism, exacerbated during the research period of elections, bearing sometimes a post-socialist load, which adds to the complexities of articulating national and European identities for the Czech citizenry.

The scrutiny of how Europe is discursively constructed through its people and its insti-

tutions allowed tapping into the complexities of national and supranational identities and identifications, in our case in relation to the Czech, and highlight their ideological embeddedness. As these identifications and constructions are product of political struggle, the combined exploration of the institutional and the popular in the construction of Europe and of European identities calls attention to the tensions and contradictions in the articulation of these identities. It further points to the attachment of both institutional and non-institutional actors to the dominant ideologies that feed nation-centrism and right-wing nationalism.

Our analysis of the Czech case showed how the already strong identification with the national identity is gaining further (online) prominence, and how Europe becomes activated as a constitutive outside for the construction of the Czech national identity. The research points also to the specificities of such explorations, that always need to become an integral part of the analysis, as the particular historical, social, political and cultural environment produces unique outcomes. Furthermore, time and research specificity need also to be considered, avoiding generalizations. As previously mentioned, the research period was dominated by parliamentary elections in the Czech Republic. The polarization and dominance of populist and right-wing voices during that period cannot be automatically considered as the norm for all periods and social media platforms. Moreover, the research findings point to populist, extreme-right, Eurosceptic voices being popular on mainstream social media platforms, in the Czech Republic, which also merits further exploration. This implies that one needs to be careful in making claims of broader societal relevance and impact, also because high popularity of an ideology on one social media platform does not automatically translate into its hegemonization in the entire social realm.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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